

The Number of Rational Points on Elliptic Curves $y^2 = x^3 + b^2$ Over Finite Fields

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Abstract—Let p be a prime number, \mathbf{F}_p be a finite field and let Q_p denote the set of quadratic residues in \mathbf{F}_p . In the first section we give some notations and preliminaries from elliptic curves. In the second section, we consider some properties of rational points on elliptic curves $E_{p,b} : y^2 = x^3 + b^2$ over \mathbf{F}_p , where $b \in \mathbf{F}_p^*$. Recall that the order of $E_{p,b}$ over \mathbf{F}_p is $p+1$ if $p \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$. We generalize this result to any field \mathbf{F}_p^n for an integer $n \geq 2$. Further we obtain some results concerning the sum $\sum_{[x]} E_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_p)$ and $\sum_{[y]} E_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_p)$, the sum of x - and y -coordinates of all points (x, y) on $E_{p,b}$, and also the the sum $\sum_{(x,0)} E_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_p)$, the sum of points $(x, 0)$ on $E_{p,b}$.

Keywords—elliptic curves over finite fields, rational points on elliptic curves.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mordell began his famous paper [8] with the words *Mathematicians have been familiar with very few questions for so long a period with so little accomplished in the way of general results, as that of finding the rational points on elliptic curves.* The history of elliptic curves is a long one, and exciting applications for elliptic curves continue to be discovered. Recently, important and useful applications of elliptic curves have been found for cryptography [4,6,7], for factoring large integers [5] and for primality proving [2,3]. The mathematical theory of elliptic curves was also crucial in the proof of Fermat's Last Theorem [13].

Let q be a positive integer, \mathbf{F}_q be a finite field and let $\overline{\mathbf{F}}_q$ denote the algebraic closure of \mathbf{F}_q with $\text{char}(\overline{\mathbf{F}}_q) \neq 2, 3$. An elliptic curve E over \mathbf{F}_q is defined by an equation

$$E : y^2 = x^3 + ax + b,$$

where $a, b \in \mathbf{F}_q$ and $4a^3 + 27b^2 \neq 0$. We can view an elliptic curve E as a curve in projective plane \mathbf{P}^2 , with a homogeneous equation $y^2z = x^3 + axz^2 + bz^3$, and one point at infinity, namely $(0, 1, 0)$. This point ∞ is the point where all vertical lines meet. We denote this point by O . Let

$$E(\mathbf{F}_q) = \{(x, y) \in \mathbf{F}_q \times \mathbf{F}_q : y^2 = x^3 + ax + b\} \cup \{O\}$$

denote the set of rational points (x, y) on E . Then it is a subgroup of E . The order of $E(\mathbf{F}_q)$, denoted by $\#E(\mathbf{F}_q)$, is defined as the number of the rational points on E and is given

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by

$$\begin{aligned} \#E(\mathbf{F}_q) &= 1 + \sum_{x \in \mathbf{F}_q} \left(1 + \frac{x^3 + ax + b}{\mathbf{F}_q} \right) \\ &= q + 1 + \sum_{x \in \mathbf{F}_q} \left(\frac{x^3 + ax + b}{\mathbf{F}_q} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\left(\frac{\cdot}{\mathbf{F}_q}\right)$ denotes the Legendre symbol (for further details on rational points on elliptic curves see [9,10,12]).

Let p be a prime number and let $q = p^n$ for integer $n > 1$. Let

$$N = q + 1 - a. \quad (2)$$

Then a is called the trace of Frobenius and satisfies the inequality

$$|a| \leq 2\sqrt{q} \quad (3)$$

known as the Hasse interval [12, p.91]. Then there is an elliptic curve E defined over \mathbf{F}_q such that $\#E(\mathbf{F}_q) = N$ if and only if a satisfies (3) and also satisfies one of the following (see [12, p.92]):

- 1) $\text{gcd}(a, p) = 1$
- 2) n is even and $a = \pm 2\sqrt{q}$
- 3) n is even, p is not equivalent to $1 \pmod{3}$ and $a = \pm\sqrt{q}$
- 4) n is odd, $p = 2, 3$ and $a = \pm p^{(n+1)/2}$
- 5) n is even, p is not equivalent to $1 \pmod{4}$ and $a = 0$
- 6) n is odd and $a = 0$

The formula (1) can be generalized to any field \mathbf{F}_{q^n} for an integer $n \geq 2$. Let $\#E(\mathbf{F}_q) = q + 1 - a$ and let

$$X^2 - aX + q = (X - \alpha)(X - \beta). \quad (4)$$

Then the order of E over \mathbf{F}_{q^n} is

$$\#E(\mathbf{F}_{q^n}) = q^n + 1 - (\alpha^n + \beta^n). \quad (5)$$

II. THE NUMBER OF RATIONAL POINTS ON ELLIPTIC CURVE $y^2 = x^3 + b^2$ OVER \mathbf{F}_p .

In [11], the third author consider the elliptic curves $E : y^2 = x^3 - t^2x$ over a finite field \mathbf{F}_p , where p is a prime number and $t \in \mathbf{F}_p^*$. He obtain some results concerning rational points on E .

In the present paper we consider the elliptic curves

$$E_{p,b} : y^2 = x^3 + b^2 \quad (6)$$

over \mathbf{F}_p . Recall that if $p \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$, then $\#E(\mathbf{F}_p) = p + 1$. But when $p \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$, then there is no rule for $\#E(\mathbf{F}_p)$. Therefore we assume that $p \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$ throughout the paper.

First we give the following theorem.

Theorem 2.1: Let $p \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$ be a prime. If $(p-1, 3) = 1$, then the congruence

$$x^3 \equiv b \pmod{p}$$

has a solution for each $b \in \mathbf{F}_p$, that is every $b \in \mathbf{F}_p$ is a cubic residue.

Proof: Let $p \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$. Then $p = 5 + 6q$ for some $q \in \mathbf{Z}$. Then

$$(p-1, 3) = (6q+4, 3) = 1.$$

Hence we have either $p = 3$ or $p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$. So if $p = 3$, then

$$0^3 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, 1^3 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, 2^3 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$$

in \mathbf{F}_3 . Therefore every $b \in \mathbf{F}_3$ is a cubic residue.

If $p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, then $p = 2 + 3q$ for $q \in \mathbf{Z}$. Therefore the norm of p is

$$|p| = p\bar{p} = (2+3q)(2+3q) = 9q^2 + 12q + 4$$

and hence

$$\frac{|p|-1}{3} = 3q^2 + 4q + 1.$$

So we have

$$b^{\frac{|p|-1}{3}} \equiv b^{3q^2+4q+1}.$$

Hence $b^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$ by Fermat's Little Theorem. So

$$b^{p-1} \equiv b^{3q+2-1} \equiv b^{3q+1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}.$$

Consequently

$$b^{\frac{|p|-1}{3}} \equiv (b^{3q+1})^{q+1} \equiv 1^{q+1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}.$$

Now let $1 \leq b \leq p-1$ and let $0 \leq q \leq p-2$. Let g be a primitive root modulo p such that $g^q \equiv b \pmod{p}$. Hence there are integers u and v such that

$$3u + (p-1)v = 1 \tag{7}$$

since $(3, p-1) = 1$. If we take $x = uq$ and $y = vq$, then (7) becomes

$$3x + (p-1)y = q.$$

Therefore we get

$$\begin{aligned} b &\equiv g^q \pmod{p} \\ &\equiv g^{sx+(p-1)y} \pmod{p} \\ &\equiv (g^x)^3 (g^{p-1})^y \pmod{p} \\ &\equiv (g^x)^3 \pmod{p} \end{aligned}$$

since $g^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$, that is, b is a cubic residue modulo p . Further $0^3 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. Therefore all elements of \mathbf{F}_p are cubic residues. ■

We know that the order of $E_{p,b} : y^2 = x^3 + b^2$ over \mathbf{F}_p is $\#E_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_p) = p+1$. Now we generalize this result to \mathbf{F}_{p^n} for a positive integer $n \geq 2$.

Theorem 2.2: Let $E_{p,b} : y^2 = x^3 + b^2$ be an elliptic curve over \mathbf{F}_p . Then

$$\#E_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_{p^n}) = \begin{cases} (p^{\frac{n}{2}} - 1)^2 & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{4} \\ p^n + 1 & \text{if } n \equiv 1, 3 \pmod{4} \\ (p^{\frac{n}{2}} + 1)^2 & \text{if } n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}. \end{cases}$$

Proof: Let $E_{p,b} : y^2 = x^3 + b^2$. Then the order of $E_{p,b}$ over \mathbf{F}_p is $\#E_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_p) = p+1$. Therefore $a = 0$ by (2). Then

$$\begin{aligned} X^2 + p &= (X - i\sqrt{p})(X + i\sqrt{p}) \\ &= (X - \alpha)(X - \beta) \end{aligned}$$

for $\alpha = i\sqrt{p}$ and $\beta = -i\sqrt{p}$.

Let $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, say $n = 4k$ for an integer $k \geq 1$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha^n + \beta^n &= (i\sqrt{p})^{4k} + (-i\sqrt{p})^{4k} \\ &= i^{4k}(\sqrt{p})^{4k} + (-i)^{4k}(\sqrt{p})^{4k} \\ &= p^{2k} + p^{2k} \\ &= 2p^{2k} \\ &= 2p^{\frac{n}{2}}. \end{aligned}$$

So

$$\begin{aligned} \#E_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_{p^n}) &= p^n + 1 - (\alpha^n + \beta^n) \\ &= p^n + 1 - 2p^{\frac{n}{2}} \\ &= (p^{\frac{n}{2}} - 1)^2 \end{aligned}$$

by (5).

Let $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, say $n = 1 + 4k$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha^n + \beta^n &= (i\sqrt{p})^{4k+1} + (-i\sqrt{p})^{4k+1} \\ &= i^{4k+1}(\sqrt{p})^{4k+1} + (-i)^{4k+1}(\sqrt{p})^{4k+1} \\ &= i(\sqrt{p})^{4k+1} - i(\sqrt{p})^{4k+1} \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

So $\#E_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_{p^n}) = p^n + 1$.

Let $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, say $n = 2 + 4k$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha^n + \beta^n &= (i\sqrt{p})^{4k+2} + (-i\sqrt{p})^{4k+2} \\ &= i^{4k+2}(\sqrt{p})^{4k+2} + (-i)^{4k+2}(\sqrt{p})^{4k+2} \\ &= -p^{2k+1} - p^{2k+1} \\ &= -2p^{2k+1} \\ &= -2p^{\frac{n}{2}}. \end{aligned}$$

So $\#E_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_{p^n}) = p^n + 1 + 2p^{\frac{n}{2}} = (p^{\frac{n}{2}} + 1)^2$.

Finally, let $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, say $n = 3 + 4k$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha^n + \beta^n &= (i\sqrt{p})^{4k+3} + (-i\sqrt{p})^{4k+3} \\ &= i^{4k+3}(\sqrt{p})^{4k+3} + (-i)^{4k+3}(\sqrt{p})^{4k+3} \\ &= -i(\sqrt{p})^{4k+3} + i(\sqrt{p})^{4k+3} \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

So $\#E_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_{p^n}) = p^n + 1$. ■

Example 2.1: Let $E_{11,2} : y^2 = x^3 + 4$ be an elliptic curve over \mathbf{F}_{11} . Then the order of $E_{11,2}$ over \mathbf{F}_{11^n} is

$$\#E_{11,2}(\mathbf{F}_{11^n}) = \begin{cases} 214329600 & \text{for } n = 8 \\ 2357947692 & \text{for } n = 9 \\ 285311670612 & \text{for } n = 11 \\ 25937746704 & \text{for } n = 10. \end{cases}$$

Let $[x]$ and $[y]$ denote the x -coordinates and y -coordinates of the points (x, y) on $E_{p,b}$, respectively. Then we have the following results.

Theorem 2.3: The sum of $[x]$ on $E_{p,b}$ is

$$\sum_{[x]} E_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_p) = \sum_{[x]} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \right) .x$$

Proof: We know that

$$\left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x^3 + b^2 = 0 \\ 1 & \text{if } x^3 + b^2 \in Q_p \\ -1 & \text{if } x^3 + b^2 \notin Q_p. \end{cases}$$

Let $\left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = 0$. Then $x^3 + b^2 = 0$. Hence the cubic equation $x^3 + b^2 = 0$ has only one solution $x = \sqrt[3]{-b^2}$. Therefore

$$y^2 \equiv 0(\text{mod } p) \Leftrightarrow y \equiv 0(\text{mod } p).$$

So for such a point x , we have a point $(x, 0)$ on $E_{p,b}$. Therefore we get $(x + 0) .x = x$ is added to the sum.

Let $\left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = 1$. Then $x^3 + b^2$ is a square in \mathbf{F}_p . Let $x^3 + b^2 = t^2$ for any $t \in \mathbf{F}_p^*$. Then

$$y^2 \equiv t^2(\text{mod } p) \Leftrightarrow y \equiv \pm t(\text{mod } p),$$

that is, for any point (x, t) on $E_{p,b}$, the point $(x, -t)$ is also on $E_{p,b}$. Therefore for each point (x, y) , we have $(1 + 1) .x = 2x$ is added to the sum.

Let $\left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = -1$. Then $x^3 + b^2$ is not a square in \mathbf{F}_p . Then the equation $y^2 \equiv x^3 + b^2(\text{mod } p)$ has no solution. Therefore for each point (x, y) we have $(1 + (-1)) .x = 0$. ■

Theorem 2.4: The sum of $[y]$ on $E_{p,b}$ is

$$\sum_{[y]} E_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_p) = \frac{p^2 - p}{2}.$$

Proof: Let $E_{p,b} : y^2 = x^3 + b^2$ be an elliptic curve over \mathbf{F}_p . The cubic equation $x^3 + b^2 = 0$ has a solution $x = \sqrt[3]{-b^2}$. For the other values of x , we have both x and $-x$. One of these gives two points. The one makes $x^3 + b^2$ is a square, i.e. $\left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = 1$. There are $\frac{p-1}{2}$ points x in \mathbf{F}_p such that $x^3 + b^2$ is a square. Let $x^3 + b^2 = t^2$ for any $t \in \mathbf{F}_p^*$. Then we have

$$y^2 \equiv t^2(\text{mod } p) \Leftrightarrow y \equiv \pm t(\text{mod } p).$$

Hence $y = t$ and $y = p - t$. So the sum of these values of y is $t + (p - t) = p$. We know that there are $\frac{p-1}{2}$ points x in \mathbf{F}_p such that $y^2 = x^3 + b^2$ is a square. Therefore, the sum of ordinates of all points (x, y) is $p \frac{p-1}{2}$, that is

$$\sum_{[y]} E_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_p) = \frac{p^2 - p}{2}.$$

Theorem 2.5: Let $\mathbf{E}_{p,b}$ denote the set of the family of all elliptic curves over \mathbf{F}_p . Then

$$\sum_{b \in \mathbf{F}_p^*} \#\mathbf{E}_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_p) = \frac{p^2 - 1}{2}.$$

Proof: Note that there are $\frac{p-1}{2}$ elliptic curves $E_{p,b} : y^2 = x^3 + b^2$ over \mathbf{F}_p , and also the order of $E_{p,b}$ over \mathbf{F}_p is $p + 1$,

i.e. $\#E_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_p) = p + 1$. Therefore the total number of the points (x, y) on all elliptic curves $E_{p,b}$ in $\mathbf{E}_{p,b}$ over \mathbf{F}_p is

$$\sum_{b \in \mathbf{F}_p^*} \#\mathbf{E}_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_p) = (p + 1) \frac{p - 1}{2} = \frac{p^2 - 1}{2}.$$

We can give the following two theorems for the rational points $(x, 0)$ on $E_{p,b}$.

Theorem 2.6: Let $E_{p,b} : y^2 = x^3 + b^2$ be an elliptic curve over \mathbf{F}_p , and let $(x, 0)$ be a point on $E_{p,b}$. Then

$$x \in Q_p \Leftrightarrow p \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4)$$

and

$$x \notin Q_p \Leftrightarrow p \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4).$$

Proof: Let $(x, 0)$ be a point on $E_{p,b}$ and let $x \in Q_p$. Then $x^3 \equiv -b^2(\text{mod } 4)$ since $0 \equiv x^3 + b^2(\text{mod } 4)$, and $x^3 = x^2 .x \in Q_p$. Note that $-b^2 \in Q_p$ if and only if $-1 \in Q_p$, and hence $p \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4)$.

Conversely, let $p \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4)$, and let $(x, 0)$ be a point on $E_{p,b}$. Then $x^3 \equiv -b^2(\text{mod } 4)$. Since $-1 \in Q_p$ and $b^2 \in Q_p$, we have $x^3 \in Q_p$ and hence $x \in Q_p$.

The second assertion can be proved as in the same way that the first assertion was proved. ■

Theorem 2.7: Let $E_{p,b} : y^2 = x^3 + b^2$ be an elliptic curve over \mathbf{F}_p , and let $(x, 0)$ be a point on $E_{p,b}$.

1) If $p \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4)$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{(x,0)} E_{p,b} &= \sum_{t \in Q_p} t \\ &= \frac{p(p-1)(p+1)}{24} \end{aligned}$$

2) If $p \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4)$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{(x,0)} E_{p,b} &= \sum_{t \notin Q_p} t \\ &= \frac{p(p-1)(11-p)}{24}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof: 1) Let $p \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4)$. Then we proved in Theorem 2.6 that there exists only one point $x \in Q_p$ such that $(x, 0)$ is a point on $E_{p,b}$. We know that there are $\frac{p-1}{2}$ elements in Q_p . Therefore there are $\frac{p-1}{2}$ points $(x, 0)$ on $E_{p,b}$. Consequently the sum of x -coordinates of all points $(x, 0)$ on $E_{p,b}$ is equal to the sum of all elements in Q_p , that is

$$\sum_{(x,0)} E_{p,b} = \sum_{t \in Q_p} t. \tag{8}$$

Let $U_p = \{1, 2, \dots, p - 1\}$ be the set of units in \mathbf{F}_p . Then then taking squares of elements in U_p , we would obtain

$$Q_p = \{1, 4, 9, \dots, \left(\frac{p-1}{2}\right)^2\}.$$

Then the sum of all elements in Q_p is

$$1 + 4 + 9 + \dots + \frac{p^2 - 2p + 1}{4} = \frac{p(p-1)(p+1)}{24}. \tag{9}$$

(8) and (9) yield that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{(x,0)} E_{p,b} &= \sum_{t \in Q_p} t \\ &= \frac{p(p-1)(p+1)}{24}. \end{aligned}$$

2) Let $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. Then there exists a point $x \notin Q_p$ such that $(x, 0)$ is a point on $E_{p,b}$. We know that there are $\frac{p-1}{2}$ elements in $U_p - Q_p$. Therefore there are $\frac{p-1}{2}$ points $(x, 0)$ on $E_{p,b}$. Consequently the sum of x -coordinates of all points $(x, 0)$ on $E_{p,b}$ is equal to the sum of all elements in $U_p - Q_p$, that is

$$\sum_{(x,0)} E_{p,b} = \sum_{t \in U_p - Q_p} t. \quad (10)$$

We proved as above that the sum of all elements in Q_p is

$$\frac{p(p-1)(p+1)}{24}.$$

Therefore the sum of all elements in $U_p - Q_p$ is

$$\frac{p(p-1)}{2} - \frac{p(p-1)(p+1)}{24} = \frac{p(p-1)(11-p)}{24}. \quad (11)$$

Applying (10) and (11) we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{(x,0)} E_{p,b} &= \sum_{t \notin Q_p} t \\ &= \frac{p(p-1)(11-p)}{24}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.8: Let $b \in Q_p$ be a fixed number. Then the order of $E_{p,b}$ over \mathbf{F}_p is

$$\#E_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_p) = \frac{p-3}{2}$$

for $x \in Q_p$.

Proof: Let $b \in Q_p$ be fixed and let $x \in Q_p$. Recall that the order of an elliptic curve E over a finite field \mathbf{F}_p is given in (1) as

$$\begin{aligned} \#E(\mathbf{F}_p) &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \right) \\ &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} 1 + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Note that the set of b^2x^3 's and the set of x^3 's are same when $p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, that is,

$$\sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right).$$

Therefore we can rewrite (12) as

$$\begin{aligned} \#E(\mathbf{F}_p) &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \right) \\ &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} 1 + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

The last sum over $x \in Q_p$ can be rearranged as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2(x^3 + 1)}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \left(\frac{b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + 1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore we can rewrite (13) as

$$\begin{aligned} \#E(\mathbf{F}_p) &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \right) \\ &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} 1 + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2(x^3 + 1)}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \left(\frac{b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + 1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Note that $b^2 \in Q_p$, that is, $\left(\frac{b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = 1$. Therefore (14) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \#E(\mathbf{F}_p) &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \right) \\ &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} 1 + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2(x^3 + 1)}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \left(\frac{b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + 1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + 1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Note that x takes $\frac{p-1}{2}$ values between 1 and $p-1$ since $x \in Q_p$. So we can rewrite (15) as

$$\begin{aligned} \#E(\mathbf{F}_p) &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \right) \\ &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} 1 + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2(x^3 + 1)}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \left(\frac{b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + 1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + 1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{1 \leq x \leq p-1} \left(\frac{x^3+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right).$$

On the other hand, $\left(\frac{(p-1)^3+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = 0$ for $x = p-1$. Hence (16) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \#E(\mathbf{F}_p) &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x^3+b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \right) \\ &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} 1 + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3+b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3+b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2x^3+b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2(x^3+1)}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \left(\frac{b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{1 \leq x \leq p-1} \left(\frac{x^3+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{1 \leq x \leq p-2} \left(\frac{x^3+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

We know that all elements of \mathbf{F}_p are cubic residues by Theorem 2.1. Consequently the set of consisting of the values of x^3 is the same with the set of values of x . So we can rewrite (17) as

$$\begin{aligned} \#E(\mathbf{F}_p) &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x^3+b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \right) \\ &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} 1 + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3+b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3+b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2x^3+b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2(x^3+1)}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \left(\frac{b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{1 \leq x \leq p-1} \left(\frac{x^3+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{1 \leq x \leq p-2} \left(\frac{x^3+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{1 \leq x \leq p-2} \left(\frac{x+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

It is proved in [1, p.128] that, the number of consecutive pairs of quadratic residues in \mathbf{F}_p is given by formula

$$\eta_p = \frac{(p-4 - (-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}})}{4}. \quad (19)$$

Hence we have two cases:

Case 1: Let $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$. Then by the Chinese remainder theorem we get $p \equiv 5 \pmod{12}$. So $(-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} = 1$. Therefore

$$\eta_p = \frac{p-5}{4} \quad (20)$$

by (19). Further $-1 \in Q_p$ since $p \equiv 5 \pmod{12}$. So there are

$$\frac{p-1}{2} - 1 = \frac{p-3}{2}$$

values of x between 1 and $p-2$ lying in Q_p . Further $\frac{p-5}{4}$ values of $x+1$ are also in Q_p by (20). Consequently there are $\frac{p-5}{4}$ times $+1$ and $\frac{p-3}{2} - \frac{p-5}{4} = \frac{p-1}{4}$ times -1 . So

$$\frac{p-5}{4} - \frac{p-1}{4} = -1.$$

Therefore

$$\sum_{1 \leq x \leq p-2} \left(\frac{x+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = -1.$$

So (18) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \#E(\mathbf{F}_p) &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x^3+b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \right) \\ &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} 1 + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3+b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3+b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2x^3+b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2(x^3+1)}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \left(\frac{b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{1 \leq x \leq p-1} \left(\frac{x^3+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{1 \leq x \leq p-2} \left(\frac{x^3+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{1 \leq x \leq p-2} \left(\frac{x+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} - 1 \\ &= \frac{p-3}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Case 2: Let $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. Then by the Chinese remainder theorem we get $p \equiv 11 \pmod{12}$. So $(-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} = 1$. Therefore

$$\eta_p = \frac{p-3}{4} \quad (21)$$

by (19). Further $-1 \notin Q_p$ since $p \equiv 11 \pmod{12}$. So there are

$$\frac{p-1}{2} - 0 = \frac{p-1}{2}$$

values of x between 1 and $p-2$ lying in Q_p since $p-1 \notin Q_p$. Further $\frac{p-3}{4}$ values of $x+1$ are also in Q_p by (21).

Consequently, there are $\frac{p-3}{4}$ times $+1$ and $\frac{p-1}{2} - \frac{p-3}{4} = \frac{p+1}{4}$ times -1 . So

$$\frac{p-3}{4} - \frac{p+1}{4} = -1.$$

Therefore

$$\sum_{1 \leq x \leq p-2} \left(\frac{x+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = -1.$$

So (18) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \#E(\mathbf{F}_p) &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \right) \\ &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} 1 + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2 x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{b^2 (x^3 + 1)}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \left(\frac{b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + 1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + 1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{1 \leq x \leq p-1} \left(\frac{x^3 + 1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{1 \leq x \leq p-2} \left(\frac{x^3 + 1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{1 \leq x \leq p-2} \left(\frac{x+1}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} - 1 \\ &= \frac{p-3}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence in two cases we have

$$\#E(\mathbf{F}_p) = \frac{p-3}{2}.$$

Now we can give the following theorem for $x \in U_p - Q_p$ without giving its proof since it is similar.

Theorem 2.9: Let $b \in Q_p$ be a fixed number. Then the order of $E_{p,b}$ over \mathbf{F}_p is

$$\#E_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_p) = \frac{p+3}{2}$$

for $x \in U_p - Q_p$.

Theorem 2.10: Let $p \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$ and let $b \in U_p - Q_p$ be a fixed number. Then the order of $E_{p,b}$ over \mathbf{F}_p is

$$\#E_{p,b}(\mathbf{F}_p) = \frac{p-1}{2}$$

for $x \in Q_p$.

Proof: Note that $b \in Q_p$ if and only if $-b \in Q_p$ when $p \equiv 5 \pmod{12}$ and $b \in Q_p$ if and only if $-b \in U_p - Q_p$ when $p \equiv 11 \pmod{12}$. By (1), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \#E(\mathbf{F}_p) &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Case 1: Let $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$. Then by the Chinese remainder theorem we get $p \equiv 5 \pmod{12}$. Then the order Q_p is $\frac{p-1}{2}$ which is an even number. So we have

$$\left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = 1$$

for exactly half of the values of $x \in Q_p$, and

$$\left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = -1$$

for exactly other half of the values of $x \in Q_p$. So

$$\sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = 0.$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \#E(\mathbf{F}_p) &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + 0 \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Case 2: Let $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. Then by the Chinese remainder theorem we get $p \equiv 11 \pmod{12}$. Then $\frac{p-1}{2}$ is odd. It is easily seen that

$$\left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = 0$$

for $x = -b$. Further

$$\left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = 1$$

for exactly $\frac{p-3}{4}$ values of $x \in Q_p$, and

$$\left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = -1$$

for exactly $\frac{p-3}{4}$ values of $x \in Q_p$. So

$$\sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) = 0.$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \#E(\mathbf{F}_p) &= \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(1 + \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{x \in Q_p} \left(\frac{x^3 + b^2}{\mathbf{F}_p} \right) \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2} + 0 \\ &= \frac{p-1}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

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